

RESEARCH ARTICLE ↓

Internet Safety and Performance of Public Civil Servants in Ogoja, Cross River State

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Abstract

The study evaluated internet safety and performance of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State. The specific objectives were to: examine the relationship between information security and efficiency; evaluate the relationship between personal safety and communication of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State. The area of the study was effect of internet safety and performance of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State. Three hundred and twenty two (322) public civil servants in Ogoja, were selected for the study. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. Two hundred and sixty six (266) employees returned their questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 83 percent response rate. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Pearson correlation coefficient (r) - test statistic tool. The findings indicated information security had significant positive relationship with the efficiency of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State, $r(95, n = 266), .517 < .810, p. >.05$. Personal safety had significant positive relationship with the communication of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State, $r(95, n = 266), .443 < .726, p. >.05$. The study concluded that Information security and Personal safety had significant positive relationship with the efficiency and communication of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State. The study recommended among others that the management should ensure that data breaches, fraud, and the spread of malicious code are protected in the organization and assets against potential threats to ensure confidentiality, integrity, and availability of the organisation information.

Keywords: Internet Safety; Performance; Information Security; Personal Safety; Public Civil Servants; Cross River State

Introduction

Internet is an emerging trend in organizations both public and private to ensure high level performance. The Civil Service has embraced it in other to heighten the performance of workers (Modu, 2021). Civil servants are the main pillars of a country for effective governance (Islam, 2020). Internet safety has emerged as a crucial factor for the effectiveness of the digital workplace which can be achieved with the suitable digital alertness and organizational support from employees (Vimala and Nithya, 2022; Mbah, Ekwo, & Obi, 2016)). The digital fosters seamless communication between colleagues. Using advanced mobile technology, employees can remain in contact with their coworkers regardless of location. They can access and share information. The digitalization of the workplace will involve the use of technologies with increased efficiency and optimization. It improves the organization's technological efficacy and facilitates company stakeholders such as customers, suppliers, employees, etc. Digital transformation introduces innovation in the form of the creation of new or the modification of existing business processes, climate, and stakeholder experiences to meet shifting market demands (Selimović, Pilav-Velić, & Krndžija, 2021).

Therefore, implementing digital workplace components benefits organizations' operational efficiency, productivity, business expansion, and performance maintenance. Internet security is the defense against malicious attacks on computers, mobile devices, electronic systems, servers, and various forms of data. It is also known as information technology security and electronic information security. Suppose there are no security plans in place. In that case, hackers can easily gain access to a company's computer system, electronic and smart devices, and personal applications and misuse information about the company's assets, opportunities, risks, its stakeholders, and more (Selimović, Pilav-Velić, & Krndžija, 2021). Performance of Nigerian public service has been a major concern to policy makers in the country. This is because despite all measures put in place to arrest the performance failure, the service, it seems, has defied all approaches towards tackling the problem of inefficiency and capacity collapse (Arowolo, 2018; Nnamani, Ugwu & Oluka, 2023).

In order to utilize the possibilities of information and communication technology within the public domain and thereby further develop the electronic government, it is necessary that civil servants possess sufficient levels of Internet skills. Higher levels of these skills among professionals in the public sphere might result in better Internet usage, thus improving both productivity and efficiency (Modu, 2021).

Statement of the Problem

The performance of the civil servants towards national development is no doubt the most tasking challenges that the government of Nigeria is facing today. The public service reflects the state of the nation and no nation has been able to advance beyond its Public Service. Studies have shown that no nation can attain sustainable development for the enhancement of the living standard of the people without a properly organized public service to implement government policies. Public services are seen as so important that for moral reasons, their universal provision should be guaranteed. Nigeria is an endowed nation with material and human resources enough to drive her to socio-political and economic development.

The issue of enhancing Nigerian public service performance has been a subject of debate. The structure through which this can be achieved to a great extent depends on the capacity of the government to put together policies capable of promoting effective public service performance. The challenges faced the study includes; information security; and personal safety. Information security protects sensitive information from unauthorized activities, including inspection, modification, recording, and any disruption or destruction. The goal is to ensure the safety and privacy of critical data such as customer account details, financial data or intellectual property. However, this has been a major challenge to policy makers.

Nigeria's internet security problem reaches public organizations and private corporations, but corruption, tardiness, and bureaucracy can exacerbate the problem in public organizations. Leaving a data bucket containing crucial personal information mis-configured and unsecured can happen due to human mistakes. Giving the complexity of the situation where Nigerians are suffering in the midst of many. Despite all reforms geared towards improving the

performance of the Nigeria public sector, service delivery has remained poor. For the public service to perform effectively, it operates under some core values such as integrity, meritocracy, discipline, professionalism, patriotism, impartiality and secrecy of government information, except where the information divulged conforms to the Freedom of Information Act. In the light of the above the study evaluates on internet safety affect the performance of public civil servants in Ebonyi State.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate internet safety and performance of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State. The specific objectives were to;

- i. Examine the relationship between information security and efficiency of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State.
- ii. Evaluate the relationship between personal safety and communication of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State.

Research Questions

The following questions guided the study;

- i. What is the relationship between information security and efficiency of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State?
- ii. What is the relationship between personal safety and communication of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State?

Statement of the Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study;

- i. Information security has relationship with the efficiency of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State.
- ii. Personal safety has relationship with the communication of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State.

Significance of the Study

The study was essential for both organizations and staff because it help on the easy in handing the data. It is important because it represent the business, deal with customers and handle sensitive data. Internet security training is the most effective way of educating employees on the risks they should avoid and the steps they should take if they are unsure about what to do in certain scenarios.

Scope of the Study

The study focused on internet safety and performance of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State. The study focused on information security; and performance safety and independent variable; while efficiency; and communication were used as dependent variable of the study.

Review of the Related Literature

Conceptual Framework

Internet

The internet is a global network of billions of computers and other electronic devices. With the Internet, it's possible to access almost any information, communicate with anyone else in the world, and do much more. You can do all of this by connecting a computer to the Internet, which is also called going online (GCF Global, 2024). The Internet is a globally connected network system that facilitates communication and data services through a vast collection of private, public, business, academic, and government networks (Rouse, 2023). The Internet is the most commonly used term in today's world and plays a very important role in the everyday life of people. But there are many questions, answers to which people need to know. The Internet is decentralized, which means there is no central

authority governing its operations. To enable communication between devices, the internet relies on protocols and standards that govern how small units of data are formatted, addressed, and transmitted (Rouse, 2023; Ugwu & Mbah, 2018). The Internet is the foremost important tool and the prominent resource that is being used by almost every person across the globe.

Safety

Safety is the condition of being protected from harm or other danger. Safety can also refer to the control of recognized hazards in order to achieve an acceptable level of risk. Safety is a concept that includes all measures and practices taken to preserve the life, health, and bodily integrity of individuals (Safeopedia, 2018). In the workplace, safety is measured through a series of metrics that track the rate of near misses, injuries, illnesses, and fatalities. Safety is very important aspect for any industry as an accident-free work environment boosts the morale of the team members working in any hazardous situations (John, 2018). Recognizing these facts industries involving various hazards and risks industries prepare their own safety policy, safety manual and have a separate department/section for safety so as to create proper awareness and provide the know-how-about the safety. Safety means continuing and healthful living without injury. Safety is freedom from harm or the danger of harm. The word safety refers to the precautions people take to prevent accidents, harm, danger, damage, loss and pollution. Safety also deals with improvement in working conditions for better health. Management is responsible to provide safe working condition and individual's safety (John, 2018). Regulatory bodies such as OSHA and the NFPA mandate a variety of safety measures employers must take and have the authority to impose fines if their investigations reveal a violation of these standards. Safety is also beneficial for all organizations since, in addition to avoiding costly fines, it ensures increased productivity, better morale, and fewer lost work days (Safeopedia, 2022).

Internet Safety

Internet safety can be defined as the state of being safe and secure from online attacks and threats against one's online data and presence, including online profiles and technological devices. Internet safety is also referred to as online safety or cyber safety. It includes being protected from various online threats and risks against one's privacy as well as mental and physical well-being (Sanam, 2023). The global pervasiveness of technology, the internet, and social media has turned internet safety into a crucially important topic both for individuals and communities. Protecting and ensuring internet safety is important for preventing various types of crime, ranging from financial crimes such as credit card fraud to organized crimes such as human trafficking. Internet safety also plays a significant role in ensuring the mental and physical health of children and teenagers who spend time on social media (Sanam, 2023).

Internet safety is the practice of following actionable guidelines, understanding modern technology, and protecting your digital devices so you can defend against malicious parts of the online world (Zook, 2019). It's one of the main parts of a strong digital citizenship program in any school. That's because the internet provides near-instant satisfaction when looking up answers to questions, instructions on how to accomplish a task, and more. But it's also packed with potential dangers. Malware, phishing, scams, and drive-by downloads, misrepresentation, and old-fashioned lies hide in every possible corner online, just waiting for an opportunity to strike. Internet safety requires you to have a firm comprehension of the internet, what's on it, how it's used, and how it operates. It also emphasizes understanding the lesser-known areas of the internet, like code, webpage interactions, and secure connections. The most important part of internet safety is learning how to make safe choices (Zook, 2019).

Internet safety is the ability to understand and recognize threats that exist on the internet, as well as having the skills and knowledge to avoid these threats. This includes knowing how to keep personal information private and secure online, protecting devices from malware, avoiding harmful or illegal content, and managing online relationships safely. The Internet has made it possible to create and develop new forms of communication, including social media, which very quickly began to be used for commercial purposes (Farin, 2022). This way of disseminating information has become popular and has improved not only in the business sphere, but also in the public sector, although here new solutions have been accepted with a greater dose of reserve and mistrust (Kelly, 2018).

Components of Internet Safety used in the Study

The components of internet safety used in the study includes: information security, personal safety.

Information security

Information security covers the tools and processes that organizations use to protect information. This includes policy settings that prevent unauthorized people from accessing business or personal information. Information security protects sensitive information from unauthorized activities, including inspection, modification, recording, and any disruption or destruction. The goal is to ensure the safety and privacy of critical data such as customer account details, financial data or intellectual property. The consequences of security incidents include theft of private information, data tampering, and data deletion. Attacks can disrupt work processes and damage a company's reputation, and also have a tangible cost. Organizations must allocate funds for security and ensure that they are ready to detect, respond to, and proactively prevent, attacks such as phishing, malware, viruses, malicious insiders, and ransom ware (Murray & Margel, 2023).

The basic tenets of information security are confidentiality, integrity and availability. Every element of the information security program must be designed to implement one or more of these principles (Murray & Margel, 2023; Fletcher, 2016). Information security is the practice of protecting information by mitigating information risk (Joshi and Singh, 2017). Information security is a set of policies, procedures and principles for safeguarding digital data and other kinds of information. Information security responsibilities include establishing a set of business processes that protect information assets, regardless of how that information is formatted or whether it is in transit, being processed or at rest in storage. Generally, an organization applies information security to guard digital information as part of an overall cybersecurity program. Information security ensures that the employees have access to the data they require, while preventing unauthorized access. It can also be associated with risk management and legal regulations (Kinza & Gavin, 2023 and Eze, Edeoga, & Mbah, 2023).

Personal Safety

Personal safety refers to anything that is designed to provide a feel of safety to its possessor. The best way to define would be to quote that personal safety has no general definition rather it depends upon the situation and its various parameters (Vishal, 2015). A person may not be at direct threat from anyone, but he/she still may remain in constant fear which indicates a lack of personal safety. One of the major mistakes while ensuring personal safety is to consider only strangers as someone who can commit crime whereas the reality is mostly the opposite. A common solution as we all look towards is to eliminate all possible threats towards our personal safety from society and our surrounding which is actually next to impossible (Vishal, 2015).

In order to achieve consistent, effective personal safety in the workplace, each worker must know how to identify, assess and reduce or manage the risk of violence and aggression. Consideration and care by employers for their employees improves not only the relationship between members of the public and the employees, but also the relationship between the organisation and its staff. This approach can lead to better co-operation and loyalty between staff as well as more accurate identification of violence and aggression. This in turn can reduce incidents of stress-related absence and illness amongst staff (Lamplugh, 2018).

Performance

Performance is an accomplishment of a given task measured against preset known standards of accuracy, completeness, cost, and speed. In a contract, performance is deemed to be the fulfillment of an obligation, in a manner that releases the performer from all liabilities under the contract. Performance is viewed as the implementation of an action or one's ability. Good performance is also related with achieving the quality, quantity, cooperation, dependability and creativity. Employee performance is considered as the measures of the quality of human capital. Performance of Nigerian public service has been a major concern to policy makers and researchers as well. This is because despite all measures put in place to arrest the performance failure, the service, it seems, has

defied all approaches towards tackling the problem of inefficiency and capacity collapse (Arowolo, 2012 and Eze, Agbo & Mbah2022). Job performance becomes the most important focus of administrators and academicians because the performance level will deteriorate if the level of skill of employee drops (Osawe, 2015). Performance is an action that involves a lot of efforts aimed at achieving a purpose. Performance is measured on a given set of standards to determine how well or badly a duty or an activity is carried out. Performance is considered to be the company's ability to profit from the resources and achieve its objectives (Arkadiusz, 2022; Nnamani, Ugwu, & Oluka, 2023)). Performance involves analyzing a company's performance against its objectives and goals. In other words, organizational performance comprises real results or outputs compared with intended outputs.

Components of Performance that Form Part of the Objective

The analysis focuses on three main outcomes, first, shareholder value performance; second, financial performance; and third, market performance (Arkadiusz, 2022). The components used in the study include; communication; and efficiency.

Communication

Communication plays a vital role to every business today. It is the art of passing information from one person to another or from one department to the other. Communication is done in different forms from horizontal, vertical, formal, and informal. Employers who invest time and energy into effective communication often build trust among employees which leads to increased output, productivity and morale. In addition, employees who communicate well with the customers and colleagues are viewed as important assets to an organization (Workpay, 2019). Communication is an inseparable aspect of daily life and we cannot live without communicating with anyone. Communication can take place in both ways; either in-person communication or communication through various social media platforms. Effective communication definition is the process of exchanging or transmitting ideas, information, thoughts, knowledge, data, opinion, or messages from the sender through a selected method or channel to the receiver with a purpose that can be understood with clarity (Kevin, 2023). The utilization of digital tools and platforms has significantly enhanced communication and collaboration among civil servants, facilitating seamless connections with colleagues, superiors and stakeholders regardless of geographical barriers (Tuoi & Thanh, 2023). Consequently, this has resulted in accelerated decision-making processes, improved coordination, and enhanced dissemination of information. Effective communication plays a pivotal role in facilitating efficient information exchange, enabling the sharing of updates and knowledge among civil servants (Barrett, 2022). This, in turn, leads to better-informed decision-making and enhanced execution of tasks. Furthermore, collaboration among civil servants promotes coordinated efforts, streamlines workflows, and optimizes resource allocation, thereby fostering teamwork and augmenting work performance (Pauca & Bencomo, 2016).

Efficiency

Efficiency refers to the peak level of performance that uses the least amount of inputs to achieve the highest amount of output. Efficiency requires reducing the number of unnecessary resources used to produce a given output, including personal time and energy (Banton, Boyle & Schmitt, 2023). Efficiency is a measurable concept that can be determined using the ratio of useful output to total input. Increased efficiency minimizes the waste of resources such as physical materials, energy, and time while accomplishing the desired output. Efficiency can be defined as the ability to achieve an end goal with little to no waste, effort, or energy. Efficiency can be used in a variety of ways to describe various optimization processes. As such, analyzing efficiency can help reduce costs and increase bottom lines (Banton, Boyle & Schmitt, 2023). Efficiency measures the level of performance achieved against a standard. A high level of efficiency generates the highest possible amount of outputs with the smallest amount of inputs. A business can find itself in trouble if it pursues efficiency to an excessive extent, taking the focus of management attention away from the effectiveness of the overall corporate direction (Accounting Tools, 2023). The major roles of civil servants are in policy making, supportive in its national objectives and economic development. Efficiency is needed for civil servants at federal and states levels, since it measures the performance of tasks expected to be done, Ajayi and Ayodele (2022) explained that efficiency is a means of using minimum resources or input to achieve

maximum objective or output. In every establishment efficiency is regarded as a vital weapon for good service returns.

Conceptual Framework of the Study

Conceptual framework illustrates the expected relationship between your variables. It defines the relevant objectives for your research process and maps out how they come together to draw coherent conclusions (Swaen and George, 2022).

Source: Researcher's Field Compilation, 2024

Theoretical Framework

Victor H. Vroom (1964) developed expectancy theory. He defines motivation as a process governing choices among alternative forms of voluntary activities, a process controlled by the individual. The individual makes choices based on estimates of how well the expected results of a given behavior are going to match up with or eventually lead to the desired results. Motivation is a product of the individual's expectancy that a certain effort will lead to the intended performance, the instrumentality of this performance to achieving a certain result, and the desirability of this result for the individual, known as valence (Condrey, 2005). The expectancy theory of motivation explains the behavioral process of why individuals choose one behavioral option over the other. This theory explains that individuals can be motivated towards goals if they believe that there is a positive correlation between efforts and performance, the outcome of a favorable performance will result in a desirable reward, a reward from a performance will satisfy an important need, and/or the outcome satisfies their need enough to make the effort worthwhile.

The theory was in support with the objective two of the study, "information security and efficiency of public civil servants". Expectancy theory proposes that an individual will behave or act in a certain way because they are motivated to select a specific behavior over others due to what they expect the result of that selected behavior will be (Oliver, 1974). In essence, the motivation of the behavior selection is determined by the desirability of the outcome. However, at the core of the theory is the cognitive process of how an individual processes the different motivational elements. This is done before making the ultimate choice. The outcome is not the sole determining factor in making the decision of how to behave (Oliver, 1974).

The study was anchored on expectancy theory because the theory states that the intensity of a tendency to perform in a particular manner is dependent on the intensity of an expectation that the performance will be followed by a definite outcome and on the appeal of the outcome to the individual. Vroom's expectancy theory assumes that behavior results from conscious choices among alternatives whose purpose it is to maximize pleasure and to minimize pain. Vroom realized that an employee's performance is based on individual factors such as personality, skills, knowledge, experience and abilities.

Empirical Review

Information security and efficiency

Tenibiaje (2012) conducted a study on the impact of computer use on the efficiency of civil servants in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study sought to examine the impact of computer use on the efficiency of civil servants in Ekiti State. The study adopted a descriptive survey method. The sample consisted of 58 civil servants which were randomly selected among civil servant Ekiti State, Nigeria. T-test statistical analysis was used. The finding showed that there was no significant difference in the impact of computer on the efficiency of junior and senior civil servants as well as no significant difference in the efficiency of female and male civil servants in the use of computer.

Munawar, Abdul and Nurdasila (2020) conducted a study on the improving the efficiency of the state civil servants in the aceh government health service during the pandemic period. The study sought to examine the influence the performance of the Aceh Government Health Service's State Civil Servants. The study adopted quantitative design. The sample size of two hundred and ninety (290) was used. The finding showed that performance of the State Civil Servants in the Aceh Health Service can be enhanced by considering factors of psychological contract default, exchanges of leadership-subordinate, and policies.

Ighorhiohwunu (2021) conducted a study on the professionalism and public service delivery efficiency in Nigeria: An Empirical Analysis. The study sought to examine the relationship between professionalism and public service delivery efficiency in Oredo Local Government Secretariat, Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. A descriptive research method was adopted. The sample size of six hundred and seventy one (671) was used. Data were analyzed using correlation and linear regression analysis with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS). The findings showed that there is significant relationship between professionalism and public service delivery efficiency.

Negri and Dincă (2023) conducted a study on public sector's efficiency as a reflection of governance quality, an European Union study. The objective was to assess the efficiency of the European Union's public sector from a quality of governance approach, employing a two-step methodology. The study adopted a quantile regression estimation technique. The findings showed that governance quality can be considered an important resource in analysing public performance and that human resources, freedom, democracy, corruption.

Personal safety and communication

Musheke and Phiri (2021) conducted a study on the effects of effective communication on organizational performance based on the systems theory. The objectives of this study were to identify the factors affecting effective communication; and to devise a communication model that addresses these factors to improve organisational performance. A quantitative approach was used. The finding shows that there is a positive relationship between the channel of communication used and effective communication.

Andi, Aris, Syarifuddin, Yusi and Yusri (2022) examined on the effect of communication skills of civil servant in public service on community satisfaction. The study sought to examine the effect of the communication skills of civil servants in public service activities on community satisfaction. The study adopted a quantitative method. The data were analysis technique using a simple regression analysis and descriptive statistics. The finding showed that the communication skills of civil servants in public service activities had a significant effect on people's satisfaction.

George-Anokwuru (2023) conducted a study on the effect of transport and communications expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria. The study sought to examine the relationship between capital and recurrent expenditure on transport and communications sector on economic growth. The study used secondary data. The findings showed that in the long run, both capital and recurrent expenditure on transport and communications sector have positive and insignificant relationship with economic growth. The study concluded that it is only capital expenditure on transport and communications sector that has meaningfully contributed to increase in economic growth in Nigeria during the period of study.

Summary of the Review

The overall objective of every government is to bring about a qualitative improvement in the standard of living of its citizens and to promote growth and development generally. The realization of these noble objectives entails not only the formulation of policies but also the effective implementation of such formulated policies by the public service. Given the number of policies that have been formulated in Nigeria since independence, public institutions of development, the human and natural resources the country is blessed with, the nation is supposed to have witnessed tremendous levels of social, economic and political development.

Methodology

The area of the study was effect of internet safety and performance of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State. Three hundred and twenty-two (322) public civil servants in Ogoja, were selected for the study. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. Two hundred and sixty-six (266) employees returned their questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 83 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.76 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score (3.0 and above agreed while below 3.0 disagreed) and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Pearson correlation coefficient (r) - test statistic tool.

Data Presentation and Analyses

The Relationship between Information Security and Efficiency of Public Civil Servants in Ogoja, Cross River State.

Table 1: Responses on the relationship between information security and efficiency of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State.

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	ΣFX	- X	SD	Decision
1	The organisation has policy settings that guides the job of task done online	470 94 35.3	80 20 7.5	624 88 33.1	76 38 14.3	26 26 9.8	1276 266 100%	3.44	1.354	Agree
2	Unauthorized people are not allowed to access information that is not meant for their consumption	725 145 54.5	80 20 7.5	117 39 14.7	70 35 13.2	27 27 10.2	1019 266 100%	3.83	1.453	Agree
3	The organisation locate firms for protecting and proactively prevent phishing, malware, etc.	580 116 43.6	80 20 7.5	210 70 26.3	50 25 9.4	35 35 13.2	955 266 100%	3.59	1.449	Agree
4	There is practice of protecting information by mitigating information risk	650 130 48.9	204 51 19.2	99 33 12.4	46 23 8.6	29 29 10.9	1028 266 100%	3.86	1.389	Agree
5	Employees have access to be data they require while preventing unauthorised access	800 160 60.2	148 37 13.9	66 22 8.3	52 26 9.8	21 21 7.9	1087 280 100%	4.09	1.336	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.762	1.3962	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1, 114 respondents out of 266 representing 42.8 percent agreed that the organisation has policy settings that guide the job of task done online with mean score 3.44 and standard deviation of 1.354. Unauthorised people are not allowed to access information that is not meant for their consumption 165 respondents representing 62.0 percent agreed with mean score of 3.83 and standard deviation of 1.453. The organisation locates firms for protecting and proactively prevent phishing, malware, etc. 136 respondents representing 51.1 percent agreed with

mean score of 3.59 and standard deviation of 1.449. There is practice of protecting information by mitigating information risk 181 respondents representing 68.1 percent agreed with mean score of 3.86 and 1.389. Employees have access to be data they require while preventing unauthorised access 197 respondents representing 74.1 percent agreed with a mean score of 4.09 and standard deviation 1.336.

The relationship between personal safety and communication of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State.

Table 2: Responses on the relationship between personal safety and communication of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Each employee knows how to identify and reduce aggression	580 116 43.6	248 62 23.3	54 18 6.8	92 46 17.3	24 24 9.0	998 266 100%	3.75	1.398	Agree
2	There is a cordial relationships that promotes follow of information in the system	615 123 46.2	296 74 27.8	57 19 7.1	30 15 5.6	35 35 13.2	1033 266 100%	3.88	1.392	Agree
3	The employee reduce or manage the risk of violence ad increase cooperation	785 157 59.0	268 67 25.2	54 18 6.8	12 6 2.3	18 18 6.8	1137 266 100%	4.27	1.134	Agree
4	The relationship between management and its staff are formidable	685 137 51.5	336 84 31.6	39 13 4.9	36 18 6.8	14 14 5.3	1110 266 100%	4.17	1.133	Agree
5	Reduce incidents of stress-related absence and illness amongst staff	440 88 33.1	388 97 36.5	39 13 4.9	92 46 17.3	22 22 8.3	981 266 100%	3.69	1.313	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.952	1.0472	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2, 178 respondents out of 266 representing 66.9 percent agreed that each employee knows how to identify and reduce aggression with mean score 3.75 and standard deviation of 1.398. There is a cordial relationship that promotes follow of information in the system 197 respondents representing 74.0 percent agreed with mean score of 3.88 and standard deviation of 1.392. The employee reduce or manage the risk of violence and increase cooperation 224 respondents representing 84.2 percent agreed with mean score of 4.27 and standard deviation of 1.134. The relationship between management and its staff are formidable 221 respondents representing 83.1 percent agreed with mean score of 4.17 and 1.133. Reduce incidents of stress-related absence ad illness amongst staff 185 respondents representing 69.6 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.69 and standard deviation 1.313.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: Information security has relationship with the efficiency of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State.

Table 3: Correlations

		The organisation has policy settings that guides the job of task done online	Unauthorised people are not allowed to access information that is not meant for their consumption	The organisation locate firms for protecting and proactively prevent phishing, malware, etc	There is practice of protecting information by mitigating information risk	Employees have access to be data they require while preventing unauthorised access
The organisation has policy settings that guides the job of task done online	Pearson Correlation	1	.698**	.789**	.616**	.517**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	266	266	266	266	266
Unauthorised people are not allowed to access information that is not meant for their consumption	Pearson Correlation	.698**	1	.793**	.767**	.810**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	266	266	266	266	266
The organisation locate firms for protecting and proactively prevent phishing, malware, etc	Pearson Correlation	.789**	.793**	1	.777**	.685**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	266	266	266	266	266
There is practice of protecting information by mitigating information risk	Pearson Correlation	.616**	.767**	.777**	1	.686**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	266	266	266	266	266
Employees have access to be data they require while preventing unauthorised access	Pearson Correlation	.517**	.810**	.685**	.686**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	266	266	266	266	266

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3 is the Pearson correlation matrix on information security and efficiency of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows $.517 < .810$. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 levels (2 tailed) and implies that information security has relationship with the efficiency of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State ($r = .517 < .810$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ degree of freedom at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .517 < .810, p > .05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed $r = .517 < .810$, was greater than the table value of $.000$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we conclude information security had significant positive relationship with the efficiency of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State as reported in the probability value of ($r = .517 < .810, p > .05$).

Hypothesis Two: Personal safety has relationship with the communication of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State

Table 4: Correlations

		Each employee knows how to identify and reduce aggression	There is a cordial relationship that promotes follow of information in the system	The employee reduces or manage the risk of violence and increase cooperation	The relationship between management and its staff are formidable	Reduce incidents of stress-related absence and illness amongst staff
Each employee knows how to identify and reduce aggression	Pearson Correlation	1	.606**	.443**	.580**	.609**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	266	266	266	266	266
There is a cordial relationships that promotes follow of information in the system	Pearson Correlation	.606**	1	.623**	.726**	.562**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	266	266	266	266	266
The employee reduce or manage the risk of violence ad increase cooperation	Pearson Correlation	.443**	.623**	1	.724**	.445**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	266	266	266	266	266
The relationship between management and its staff are formidable	Pearson Correlation	.580**	.726**	.724**	1	.569**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	266	266	266	266	266
Reduce incidents of stress-related absence and illness amongst staff	Pearson Correlation	.609**	.562**	.445**	.569**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	266	266	266	266	266

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 is the Pearson correlation matrix on Personal safety and communication showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows .443 < .726. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 levels (2 tailed) and implies that Personal safety had significant positive relationship with the communication of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State (r=.443 < .726). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of r = .000 with degree of freedom at alpha level for a two-tailed test (r=.443 < .726, p>.05).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise rejects the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed r =.443 < .726 was greater than the table value of .000, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we conclude personal safety had significant positive relationship with the communication of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State as reported in the probability value of (r= .443 < .726, p>.05).

Discussion of Findings

From the result of hypothesis one, the computed $r = .517 < .810$, was greater than the table value of .000, Therefore, we concluded that information security had significant positive relationship with the efficiency of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State as reported in the probability value of ($r = .517 < .810, p > .05$). In support of the result in the literature review, Tenibiaje (2012) conducted a study on the impact of computer use on the efficiency of civil servants in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The finding showed that there was no significant difference in the impact of computer on the efficiency of junior and senior civil servants as well as no significant difference in the efficiency of female and male civil servants in the use of computer. Munawar, Abdul and Nurdasila (2020) conducted a study on improving the efficiency of the state civil servants in the government health service during the pandemic period. The finding showed that performance of the State Civil Servants in the Aceh Health Service can be enhanced by considering factors of psychological contract default, exchanges of leadership-subordinate, and policies. Ighorhiohunu (2021) conducted a study on the professionalism and public service delivery efficiency in Nigeria: An Empirical Analysis. The findings showed that there is significant relationship between professionalism and public service delivery efficiency.

From the result of hypothesis two, the computed $r = .443 < .726$ was greater than the table value of .000, Therefore, we concluded personal safety had significant positive relationship with the communication of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State as reported in the probability value of ($r = .443 < .726, p > .05$). In support of the result in the literature review, Musheke and Phiri (2021) conducted a study on the effects of effective communication on organizational performance based on the systems theory. The finding shows that there is a positive relationship between the channel of communication used and effective communication. Andi et al. (2022) examined on the effect of communication skills of civil servant in public service on community satisfaction. The finding showed that the communication skills of civil servants in public service activities had a significant effect on people's satisfaction.

Summary of Findings

- i. Information security had significant positive relationship with the efficiency of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State, $r(95, n = 266), .517 < .810, p > .05$.
- ii. Personal safety had significant positive relationship with the communication of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State, $r(95, n = 266), .443 < .726, p > .05$.

Conclusion

The study concluded that Information security and Personal safety had significant positive relationship with the efficiency and communication of public civil servants in Ogoja, Cross River State. Internet safety is the ability to understand and recognize threats that exist on the internet, as well as having the skills and knowledge to avoid these threats. This includes knowing how to keep personal information private and secure online, protecting devices from malware, avoiding harmful or illegal content, and managing online relationships safely. The Internet has made it possible to create and develop new forms of communication, including social media, which very quickly began to be used for commercial purposes.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were proffered

- i. The management should ensure that data breaches, fraud, and the spread of malicious code are protected in the organization and assets against potential threats to ensure confidentiality, integrity, and availability of the organisation information.
- ii. The public civil servants should practice situational awareness as this will prevent accidents, injuries, or any potential threats that may arise and effectively reduce risk and discourage those around them to commit crimes.

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